

Tilos, the first autonomous renewable green island in Mediterranean: A Horizon 2020 project

Gilles Notton¹, M-L Nivet¹, Dimitris Zafirakis², Fabrice Motte¹, Cyril Voyant¹, Alexis Fouilloy¹, Christophe Paoli¹

¹Laboratory Sciences for Environment UMR CNRS 6134, University of Corsica Pasquale Paoli, Centre Georges Peri, Route des sanguinaires, Ajaccio, France ; email : notton@univ-corse.fr, nivet@univ-corse.fr, motte_f@univ-corse.fr, voyant@univ-corse.fr, fouilloy_a@univ-corse.fr,

²Soft Energy Applications and Environmental Protection Laboratory, Mechanical Engineering Department, Technological Educational Institute of Piraeus, P.O. Box 41046, Athens 12201, Greece; email: dzaf@teipir.gr

Abstract— This paper presents the project Tilos consisting in maximizing the use of clean (renewable) energy sources for covering the electricity needs of the Tilos island in Greece. The objectives of this Horizon 2020 project are presented and a synthesis of the realized work two years after the beginning of the project is shown.

Keywords—green island; autonomous system; renewable energy; smart-grid; energy management.

I. INTRODUCTION AND GENERAL OVERVIEW

Project TILOS “Technology Innovation for the Local Scale, Optimum Integration of Battery Energy Storage” develops solutions for reaching the goal of the European Agenda 2020 of 20% renewable energy generation and the objectives of reduce greenhouse gas emissions up to 80-95% by 2050. European islands offer great potential for increasing renewable energy generation, but many of them in Southern Europe have no or limited grid connection to the mainland. In this context, generated renewable energy cannot be readily exported to the mainland and must be curtailed.

TILOS is an European Horizon 2020 project which is program for financing the research and the innovation in the European Union for the period 2014-2020. The EU Framework Program H2020 covers three sections: excellent science, industrial leadership and societal challenges. The TILOS project was classified in third position in section societal challenges, sub-topic of secure, clean and efficient energy: Local / small-scale storage-LCE-08-2014, the total cost of the project is 13.74 M€ for an European grant of 11 M€; it began in February 2015 for 4 years.

The main objective of the TILOS project, as an innovation action, is to maximize the use of clean (renewable) energy sources in covering the electricity needs of the Tilos island. The participation of the Tilos inhabitants in this project will contribute towards the protection of the environment, the reduction of the island’s carbon footprint, the fight against climate change and the development and promotion of sustainable energy models aiming at achieving increased energy autonomy.

In this context, a new prototype, hybrid system for electricity production and storage consisting of a 800 kW wind turbine, a 160 kW photovoltaic park and a 2.4 MWh/800 kW NaNiCl₂ FIAMM battery for energy storage, was designed and is being

constructed. A smart micro-grid, coordinating the operation of the system, is also developed in order to achieve the highest possible electricity autonomy and balance between intermittent Renewable Energy System (RES) like wind and PV, electricity production and electricity demand.

The TILOS project focuses on island regions which constitute high priority areas. Apart from Tilos, other participating islands include Pellworm (Germany), La Graciosa (Spain) and Corsica (France). The overall idea is to create a special platform that will enable technological know-how transfer between islands, by exploiting the experience gained through the operation of the smart grid system of Pellworm, and by offering new hypothesis-driven studies for the development of similar systems in other islands.

II. THE TILOS ISLAND

Tilos is a small Greek island located at the south-eastern part of the Aegean Sea and belongs to the far-remote complex of Dodecanese. The island size is approximately 64 km² and its coastal perimeter is almost 63 km, with its terrain being basically semi-mountainous and mountainous, except for a long valley extending from the island center to its south. On the island, there exist two main communities, namely Megalo Chorio (north part of the island) and Livadia (south-eastern part of the island), with the total island permanent population reaching approximately 533 habitants (255 and 278 respectively) and increasing considerably (x3) during the summer period due to tourists’ arrivals. The current electricity needs of Tilos (about 3.2 GWh/year, annual peak demand about 1MW) are covered exclusively by the operation of the oil-fired power station of Kos island (in the north of Tilos), through an interconnector (undersea cable of 20kV) that reaches the north side of the island after first crossing through Nisyros island (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Tilos Island situation, map and electrical connection

Owed to persistent faults of the undersea cable, the island often suffers from black-outs that can last for time periods even in the order of 15-30 min (especially during the summer period). The last one lasted 7h30 in October 2016. To this end, despite the fact that a back-up diesel generator of 1.45MW does exist on the north part of the island to face similar events, it cannot be directly dispatched since it is manually operated. Concerning the breakdown of energy needs, out of the total electricity consumption of approximately 3.2 GWh, almost 300 MWh derive from public-use loads such as street lighting, water pumping and bores, with the rest being attributed to the local residential and service sector. This is largely owed to the fact that due to the mild climate conditions, the islanders largely rely on the operation of air conditioning units for both space heating and cooling needs, while it is approximately 1/3 of the local building sector that uses electrical water heaters for satisfying hot water needs.

Alongside that, the availability of renewable energies resources on the island of Tilos is quite high. The island benefits of a good solar and wind cover. The renewable energy maps are presented in Fig. 2, with the Global irradiation and solar electricity potential in Greece on the left, and Average Wind Speed map for the local region around Tilos, on the right.

III. PROJECT STRUCTURE AND PARTNERS

The Tilos project is divided in 12 work packages (WPs), each of them regrouping several partners. The work plan comprises two main stages of implementation. The first one is the stage of *System Setup* and the second one is the stage of *System Demonstration & Application results*. Between the two implementation stages, development of the Energy Management System and Simulator (WP7) is dedicated to the optimum operation of the smart micro-grid. Fig. 3 presents the repartition of the work packages.

Tilos is a multinational European demonstration and research project engaging 13 participating enterprises and institutes (4 industrial partners, 7 academic and research partners, 2 distribution system operators and 1 non-governmental organization) from 7 European states (Germany, Greece, United Kingdom, Sweden, Italy, Spain and France) as seen in Fig. 4.

The coordinator of this project is the Technological Educational Institute of Piraeus (TEIP) from Athens in Greece.

Fig. 2. Solar and wind potential quality for the island of Tilos

Fig. 3. Structure of the project and repartition of work packaging.

Fig. 4. The Tilos consortium.

IV. THE OBJECTIVES

Acknowledging the security of supply problems faced by the islanders due to the insufficient grid interconnection with the electricity system of Kos, as well as the high-quality solar potential and the medium-high quality wind potential of Tilos, the proposed energy solution suggests application of the TILOS system through the development of a microgrid in the south part of the island that will mainly serve the community of Livadia (annual energy consumption in the order of 1.5 GWh and peak demand in the order of 450 kW).

The main objective consists to provide the electricity for this island using a hybrid photovoltaic/wind/storage energy system shown on Fig. 5. This hybrid system will use as a storage a prototype battery system based on NaNiCl₂ batteries that will support the operation of a smart micro-grid on the basis of multiple tasks:

- Synergy with wind and PV power
- Micro-grid energy management
- Maximization of RES penetration
- Grid stability
- Export of guaranteed energy
- Ancillary services to the main grid
- Synergy with Demand Side Management (DSM).

Fig. 5. Configuration of the system

The high-temperature NaNiCl_2 battery will support both stand-alone and grid-connected operation, while proving its interoperability with the rest of micro-grid components, such as smart meters, demand side management devices and distributed, residential heat storage coordinated under the energy management system of TILOS system. More precisely, the main components of the proposed solution are given in the following, informed also by a preliminary sizing study undertaken by Younicos, Eunice and TEIP.

V. DESCRIPTION OF THE INFRASTRUCTURE

The hybrid power station will comprise of:

- A 800 kWe wind turbine, to ensure minimum environmental impacts and also exploit the high quality wind potential of the island together with the local solar potential.
- A 160 kW PV park that will provide maximum power output when most necessary, i.e. during the peak load summer period and that will also offer the potential to provide guaranteed energy amounts (on a daily basis) to the macro-grid.
- A NaNiCl_2 battery storage of 2MWh useful storage capacity, used for multiple tasks including energy balance of the micro-grid to increase RES penetration, micro-grid stability and frequency control, increased micro-grid security of supply, export of guaranteed energy amounts (if possible on a daily basis) and provision of ancillary services to the upper (main) electricity grid.
- Advanced inverters, optimally interfaced with the battery components, for achieving both support and smooth transition between the two different modes of operation, i.e. stand-alone and grid-connected, to the central-upper electricity system.
- Distributed heat storage, achieved through the centralized, remote control of domestic electrical water heaters for both exploiting periods of RES energy surplus and encounter periods of energy deficits.
- Smart meters and DSM devices to be installed in selected loads of the Livadia area demand side so as to allow grid frequency and voltage regulation along with short-term energy management for achieving optimum battery storage operation through the control of residential (e.g. air conditioners and fridges) and community-level loads (e.g. water pumping).
- Three weather stations in order to collect detailed, on-site measurements of wind speed and direction, solar irradiance, air temperature and pressure, humidity, etc.

- A Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition (SCADA) based operation center that will coordinate operation of the entire system using the Microgrid Energy Management System (MEMS).

Following the development of the system, the demonstration phase will include three different test modes of operation :

- A: Stand-alone microgrid-100% self-sufficient;
- B: Increased energy autonomy levels (~75%) allowing for cable imports;
- C: Energy exchange through the sea cable under market terms

VI. PROGRESS REPORT

The project has begun with the choice of the best locations for the PV and Wind farms. To achieve these choices, full equipped weather stations for the collection of the necessary meteorological data including wind speed, solar radiation, ambient temperature, etc. at 1min interval, was installed on the island (Fig. 6). At the same time two load measuring devices were installed at two different points of the Tilos island electricity grid (Fig. 7) allowing grid study and preliminary simulations.

In the meantime, battery system specifications have also been provided in order to determine the final system configuration and layout. Tests on batteries have then been performed, including initial characterization, calculation of the energy capacities and efficiency at different power rates, impact of the different environmental and internal battery temperatures, identification and tuning of the state of energy parameters.

Fig. 6. Full year wind speed measurements at different heights from Tilos island (01/01/2015 - 31/12/2015)

Fig. 7. Full Year Dataset of Horizontal Plane Solar Radiation Measurements from Tilos Island (01/01/2015 - 31/12/2015).

Fig. 8. Load consumption measurements on Tilos

Fig. 9. SCADA container installation on Tilos Island

Based on measured data of local load demand [4], wind speed [1] and solar radiation [2, 3], preliminary forecasting models have been developed for Tilos island, principally with the use of Artificial Neural Networks.

At the same time a forecasting server architecture has been implemented in order to be ready to host the forecasting models and to schedule their executions.

To validate the energy management algorithms of the TILOS system operation, a dedicated microgrid simulator is developed by the TILOS team. In a parallel work stream, the TILOS team also looks at the development of the Extended Microgrid Simulator, suitable for the conduction of feasibility studies and able to simulate different kinds of RES-storage configurations, for both stand-alone and market-based applications. Design features of the latter are currently under elaboration by the TILOS team, with the main goal being to produce a user-friendly tool that can enable local communities to evaluate the potential for the establishment of energy schemes similar to the one of TILOS.

The Production License for the 1st ever Battery-based Wind-PV Hybrid Power Station in Greece issued from the Greek Regulatory Authority for Energy (RAE) for the TILOS hybrid power station, has been obtained on May 13th, 2016.

In September 2016, the microgrid SCADA Control Room (container, Fig. 8) has been installed on the island of Tilos. At the same time, communication between the SCADA and existing measuring equipment, including the 3 weather stations and 2 new grid load meters, was effectively established.

In November 2016 training seminars, informing the local habitants on the installation and use of the Smart Metering & DSM Panels took place, before almost 150 Smart Metering & DSM Panels were shipped to Tilos in December 2016.

In January 2017, after the reception of Approval of Environmental Terms for the installation of the hybrid power station and wind turbine contract, earth works started on site.

The commissioning stage is expected to start early 2017 and be completed in the first semester of 2017, followed by the project demo period.

It should be noted that throughout the project a stable and continuous communication channel between the local people and the project team has been promoted.

V. IMPLEMENTATION OF AN ISLAND PLATFORM

To ensure replication of the developed energy solution, a coherent island platform will be created and new case studies will be examined, including Corsica (UCPP), La Graciosa (ITC) and Pellworm (SHNG) as well as other island regions of different characteristics (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10. Replication in other islands

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was carried out in the framework of the Horizon 2020 project (H2020-LCE-2014-3 - LCE-08/2014 - 646529) TILOS “Technology Innovation for the Local Scale, Optimum Integration of Battery Energy Storage”. The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support of the European Union.

REFERENCES

- [1] K.P. Moustris, D. Zafirakis, K.A. Kavvadias and J.K. Kaldellis, "Wind power forecasting using historical data and artificial neural networks modeling", 10th Mediterranean Conference on Power Generation, Transmission, Distribution and Energy Conversion (MedPower), 6-9 November 2016, Belgrade, Serbia.
- [2] C. Voyant, G. Notton, S. Kalogirou, M.L. Nivet, C. Paoli, et al.. "Machine Learning methods for solar radiation forecasting: a review. ", Renewable Energy, Volume 105, May 2017, Pages 569–582
- [3] Cyril Voyant, Fabrice Motte, Fouilloy Alexis, Gilles Notton, Christophe Paoli, et al.. "Forecasting method for global radiation time series without training phase: comparison with other well-known prediction methodologies", Energy, Elsevier, 2016
- [4] D. Zafirakis , K.P. Moustris, D.H. Alamo and R.J. Nebot Medina, "One day-ahead prognosis of energy demand using artificial intelligence and biometeorological indices", 13th International Conference on Meteorology, Climatology and Atmospheric Physics - COMECAP. Thessaloniki, Greece. 19-21, September, 2016

